

**SUPERVISORY PRACTICES OF PROGRAM HEADS AND THEIR
RELATIONSHIP TO TEACHING EFFICACY AMONG
TEACHERS IN A HIGHER EDUCATION
INSTITUTION IN TANGUB
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Supervisory Practices of Program Heads and their Relationship to Teaching Efficacy among Teachers in a Higher Education Institution in Tangub City, Philippines

Elton John B. Embodo,* Haydee D. Villanueva
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

Supervision of teachers is essential for ensuring effective educational practices, fostering professional development, and achieving student success. The study determined the relationship of program heads' supervisory practices to the teachers' teaching efficacy. It was conducted in a community college in Tangub City, Misamis Occidental. The descriptive-correlational design was used in the study. There were 146 faculty and 361 students who served as the respondents selected through a stratified random sampling technique. The adapted Program Heads' Supervisory Practices and researcher-made Teachers' Teaching Efficacy Questionnaires were used as research instruments. Mean, Standard Deviation, and Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient were used as statistical tools to analyze the data gathered. Results revealed that the program heads were good in their supervisory practices. The teachers' teaching efficacy was very high. The program heads' supervisory practices did not influence the teacher's teaching efficacy. The strategies employed by program heads in their supervisory roles do not always translate into improved teaching efficiency. The study's findings indicate that program heads need to adopt more responsive and tailored supervisory practices that directly address the specific needs of teachers to enhance teaching efficacy. This may involve integrating targeted professional development focused on practical classroom strategies and fostering peer collaboration to share best practices. Program heads may prioritize open communication and continuous feedback mechanisms to better align their supervisory approaches with the realities of classroom instruction, ensuring that support translates into improved teaching efficiency.

Keywords: *assessment, efficacy, instruction, practices, supervision*

Introduction

Supervision of teachers is necessary to ensure adequate education practices, professional development, and student success. Recent literature highlighted that continuous supervision improves teaching quality and educational strategies (Basilio & Bueno, 2021). Supervision contributes to teacher motivation and job satisfaction, besides being more than a positive influence on teaching practices (Suriagiri et al., 2022). Supervision is vital for continuous teacher growth and adaptability in an ever-changing educational landscape and the increasingly complex needs of the students (Makin et al., 2018). More and more, the need for supportive oversight that can help manage uncertainty and promote resilience in teachers has been highlighted during unprecedented challenges in the form of the COVID-19 pandemic (UNESCO, 2020). In this context, the quality and relevance of learning practices in an increasingly challenging educational environment should be maintained through supervision.

School supervision has been widely acknowledged in education as an effective means of enhancing the educational process; hence, good supervision is paramount (Wahyu, 2020). In this context, supervision is not just about overseeing subordinates' work to ensure adherence to organizational plans and policies. It is a collaborative process that involves instructing, guiding, and observing the subordinates to ensure they work as planned. It is a systematic and continuous process that focuses on competence, is goal and growth-oriented, and is holistic, with a dual focus on the supervisee's professional development and organizational priorities (Acharya, 2019). This collaborative approach to supervision, characterized by open and honest two-way communication, sets it apart and makes it a powerful tool for educational improvement (Howard, 2021). It is a systematic and continuing process that focuses on competence, is goal and growth-oriented, holistic, and involves a dual focus on the supervisee's professional development and organizational priorities (Glanz & Hazi, 2019).

Another factor that ensures quality education is the teacher's efficacy. Self-efficacy is a person's ability to perform a job or act expected of them to accomplish a specific goal. In the case of teachers, self-efficacy refers to their confidence in their ability to change students' behavior and performance in their classrooms (Lauermaann & Hagen, 2021). Teaching efficacy of teachers is a significant phenomenon that can be regarded as one factor contributing to learning and effective teaching. It has significantly improved teaching effectiveness (Nurindah et al., 2019). Lastly, teachers' teaching efficacy significantly affects teaching methodologies, passion, dedication, and performance, which brings about success among students (Barni et al., 2019).

However, the low efficacy of teachers may be further triggered by sub-par student performance and the low efficacy of the teachers. However, teachers may feel more secure and satisfied in their jobs. They may even experience an enhancement in their overall well-being through increasing self-efficacy in classroom management (Shao, 2023). Conversely, teachers with low self-efficacy may be better informed by adequate supervision. The process of supervision of teaching and learning can make teachers feel more effective. Low teaching efficacy is correlated with both teaching quality and student learning. Hence, evaluating a school's performance should not exclude such factors (Khun-Inkeeree et al., 2020). In higher learning institutions, teachers report to program heads as their

immediate heads. Program heads supervise the teachers in instructions for better performance. They also monitor and mentor the teachers so that they can do their best (Nurzila et al., 2022). Thus, supervision among teachers is critical to ensure they deliver a quality education (Wahyu, 2020).

A study further identified the highly critical role of teachers' teaching efficacy in promoting student success and teacher well-being (Barni et al., 2019). While the existing body of research has extensively explored factors such as teacher motivation, professional development, and classroom environment, there remains a notable gap in understanding how the supervisory practices of program heads specifically impact teachers' teaching efficacy. This gap is particularly significant in the context of the increasing demands placed on educators, including curriculum changes, administrative duties, and the pressures of standardized assessments.

Despite the growing recognition of the importance of effective supervision in organizational settings, few studies have examined how the leadership practices of program heads—especially those related to feedback and mentorship—contribute to enhancing or diminishing teaching efficacy. Addressing this gap is crucial for several reasons. First, understanding this relationship could lead to more informed supervisory strategies that foster a supportive environment for teachers. Second, insights from such research could offer practical implications for school leadership training programs, highlighting the need for developing leadership styles that prioritize teacher efficacy. Finally, this research could contribute to the broader discourse on education quality, demonstrating how effective supervisory practices play an indirect but vital role in student outcomes.

A community college in Tangub City, Misamis Occidental, may submit for accreditation under the Association of Local Colleges and Universities – Commission on Accreditation (ALCU-COA) every year. With this, all the faculty may be assigned to area/s of accreditation to work on. They must comply with accreditation documents and the other deliverables. The work they do for the accreditation can be an addition to their regular workload since they also perform their other instructional workloads and classroom instruction. With this, program heads need to supervise closely the teachers to ensure the latter can manage their instructional workload, carry out their tasks well, and teach their students effectively.

In this regard, the researcher explored the critical interplay between program heads' supervisory practices and its impact on teachers' teaching efficacy. Teachers serve as the backbone of delivering quality education. However, they may experience the challenges. As such, this research aimed to fill the theoretical gap by ascertaining how supervisory practices could impact teachers' teaching efficacy. This research wanted to establish the correlation between program heads' supervisory practices and teachers' teaching efficacy, considering that teaching-efficacy plays a profound role in teaching strategies, dedication, and overall performance.

The implications of such findings for education and school management are very substantial. Proper supervisory practices by program heads may impact teachers' teaching efficacy. Such results may inform educational institutions and policymakers about investing in high-quality supervision. This would encourage developing and implementing training programs for educational leaders in supervisory work, thereby contributing to more supportive and nurturing work environments for teachers.

Research Questions

The study determined the relationship of the program heads' supervisory practices and the teachers' instructional workload management to the teachers' teaching efficacy. It was conducted in a local college in Tangub City, Misamis Occidental. The study sought to answer the following research questions:

1. What is the level of the program heads' supervisory practices as directive, collaborative, and nondirective practices?
2. What is the level of teachers' teaching efficacy in terms of delivery of instruction, administration of assessment tasks, school resource utilization, and classroom management?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the program heads' supervisory practices and teachers' teaching efficacy?

Methodology

Research Design

The used the descriptive-correlational design. Descriptive research seeks to collect data to test hypotheses or to answer questions concerning the status of the subject of the study (Gay, 1992). The correlational research design sought to ascertain relationships between two or more variables (Cherry, 2023). The design was considered appropriate in determining the relationship of the program heads' supervisory practices and the teachers' teaching efficacy.

Respondents

The first group of respondents of the study consisted of faculty members from the different departments in the institution, who rated the program heads' supervisory practices. The stratified random sampling technique was used to select the sample of students who rated the Program Heads' Supervisory Practices Questionnaire. They were grouped by institutes and then simple random sampling technique was applied to select the faculty from different institutes. The stratified random sampling was used to ensure a proportionate number of representatives from each institute. A sample size of 361 out of students served as the respondents, based the Raosoft online application used. Students who enrolled in at least 18 units were considered as respondents of the study. Faculty selection was based

on the following criteria: 1) full-time or part-time faculty; 2) at least one-semester teaching in the research locale; and 3) faculty who agreed to give their full consent to participate in the study. Faculty members who had not served the college for at least one complete semester were excluded as respondents.

The second group of respondents were the students. The stratified random sampling technique was used to select the sample of students who rated the Teaching Efficacy Questionnaire. They were grouped by programs and then simple random sampling technique was applied to select the students from different programs. The stratified random sampling was used to ensure a proportionate number of representatives from each program. A sample size of 361 out of students served as the respondents, based on the Raosoft online application used. Students who enrolled in at least 18 units were considered as respondents of the study.

Instrument

This questionnaire for Supervisory Practices of Program Heads was adapted from Hoque et al. (2020). It comprised three constructs: directive supervisory practices with ten statements, collaborative supervisory practices with ten statements, and nondirective supervisory practices with ten statements each. The instrument underwent validation by experts in the field. It also underwent pilot testing to establish its reliability. It was administered to a group of teachers who were not included as the study's respondents. The Cronbach's Alpha for the constructs: directive supervisory practices was 0.975, collaborative supervisory practices was 0.969, and nondirective supervisory practices was 0.973. The questionnaire had excellent internal consistency and was considered reliable for use as a research instrument.

This questionnaire for Teaching Efficacy was a researcher-made instrument. It was composed of four constructs: attending classes and monitoring students, delivery of instruction, administration of assessment tasks, school resource utilization, and classroom management. Each construct consisted of ten statements. This underwent validation from experts in the field, as well as pilot testing to establish its reliability. It was administered to students who were not included as the study's respondents. The Cronbach's Alpha for the constructs: delivery of instruction was 0.9348, administration of assessment tasks was 0.9565, school resource utilization was 0.9316, and classroom management was 0.9535. The questionnaire had excellent internal consistency and was considered reliable for use as the research instrument.

Procedure

The study performed specific procedures to obtain data. First, the researcher sought permission from the Dean of the Graduate School of Misamis University and the college president of the institution where the study was conducted. After obtaining approval, the researcher provided informed consent to the target respondents. Then, the researcher distributed the survey questionnaires on the program head's supervisory practices, teachers' instructional workload management, and teachers' teaching efficacy to the respondents. Two days after the distribution, the researcher retrieved the questionnaires. After all the distributed questionnaires were retrieved, the researcher tabulated the data using Microsoft Excel for statistical computation. Interpretation of the results followed.

Data Analysis

The study used the following statistical tools to analyze the data gathered: Mean and Standard Deviation. These tools were used to determine the level of the program heads' supervisory practices, teachers' instructional workload management, and teachers' teaching efficacy. Pearson Product – Moment Correlation Coefficient. This tool was used to explore the significant relationship between the level of the program heads' supervisory practices and the level of teachers' teaching efficacy.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher followed the ethical considerations of Bryman and Bell (2007). The respondents were protected from harm, and their safety was given the utmost priority. Respect for dignity ensured that the individuals had the right to be treated with dignity. The respondents' right to autonomy and freedom was respected. The respondents were informed of the nature and purpose of the research. They were asked to sign the Informed Consent form as an indication of their voluntary participation in the research. The study also dealt with protecting the privacy and confidentiality of the research data by ensuring that measures were taken to protect the identity of the respondents and the confidentiality of their information, thus maintaining the privacy of the respondents. Additionally, the anonymity of the research respondents added another layer of protection. The commitment to honesty and transparency in all research communication also underscored the commitment to having integrity throughout the research process. Finally, the respondents were assured that the research data would be discarded after the research findings would have been presented to the Dissertation Committee.

Results and Discussion

Level of the Program Heads' Supervisory Practices

Table 1 shows the level of the program heads' supervisory practices. It is shown the good (WM = 3.22; SD = 0.0321) supervisory practices of the program heads as assessed by their teachers. This finding means that the program heads oversee how the teachers carry out their daily workload to ensure effectiveness and productivity. When program heads can supervise their teachers in the most effective way possible, the teachers are more guided on how things must be done effectively, especially in teaching the students. Supervision

plays a crucial role in ensuring that teachers can carry out their tasks and perform their best to provide students with the best quality of learning.

The Table also shows that the practice of program heads in providing directive supervision among the teachers was good (MW = 3.24; SD = 0.4336). This finding means that the teachers perceived the program heads closely monitoring the teachers' instructional supervision. This type of supervision includes conducting formal evaluations, frameworks for evaluations, and effective methods of instruction, curriculum delivery, and student assessment. The program heads provide mentorship and clear guidelines regarding teaching practice. They offer specific instructional practices to resolve teaching problems and closely monitor teachers' lesson plans and classroom activities. They ensure alignment with the curriculum standards, provide clear performance goals, and make teachers accountable for expectations. They conduct scheduled classroom walkthroughs to observe teaching practices and provide timely feedback. Based on such suggestions, improvements are effectively implemented.

The Table further reveals the good collaborative supervisory practices by the program heads (WM = 3.23; SD = 0.4605). This finding means the program heads created a supportive environment through active teacher engagement. They organized team meetings for collaboration, shared the responsibilities of decision-making, and helped teachers overcome challenges in teaching. They enabled open forums for decisions on curriculum and methodologies and solicited feedback to address professional needs and celebrate collaborative accomplishments. They showed support to teacher-led ventures, encourage peer mentoring, and innovate within the educational community.

It is likewise revealed that the program heads also demonstrated a good non-directive supervisory attitude toward the teachers (MW = 3.18; SD = 0.3516). The finding implies that the program heads enabled the teachers to take responsibility for how they teach and their professional development. They created a supportive environment where the teachers felt free to decide independently on the best practices and are empowered to decide based on that. They motivated the teachers to be creative, set goals, and solve teaching-related problems by themselves. The program heads created a reflection of culture through providing facilities and opportunities for professional development. They promoted collaboration in learning and innovation practices in the teachers' profession.

From the study results, program heads generally showed a commendable level of supervisory practices, as noted by their teachers, in relation to all the constructs. Indeed, supervision by program heads is essential in guiding teachers in providing quality education to their students. Most importantly, the program heads need to exhibit good directive supervision by having a structured and systematic approach through regular assessments, teaching by guidance, and an indication of good guidelines regarding teaching.

Moreover, they may demonstrate good collaborative supervision by having the situation support teamwork, experimentation, and continuous improvement. Finally, the significance of non-directive practices is shown in empowering teachers to become owners of professional growth and in allowing them to become self-motivated, self-fulfilled, self-assessed, and self-reflective.

Teachers play a direct role in the teaching sphere, and indirectly, it reflects upon students' learning. The program heads' methods of supervising and supporting teachers in directive, collaborative, and non-directive approaches are pivotal. Strengths in teacher supervision by program heads eventually create a culture of excellence and innovation in the educational setting, which must translate into better quality education for students.

Supervision is essential in supporting teachers' growth and improving instructional quality. Adequate supervision can offer teachers feedback, guidance, and professional development opportunities, which will, in turn, lead to improved instructional practices and, thus, good student learning outcomes. Supervision is a coaching activity that helps teachers perform their duties by giving feedback and support to overcome problems in enhancing instructional quality and student outcomes (DiPaola & Wagner, 2018).

Supervision is an activity of coaching that helps teachers perform their duties by offering feedback and support to help overcome difficulties in the process of enhancing instructional quality and improving outcomes for students (Karim et al., 2021). Supervisory practices are essential to support teachers' professional development and enhance their abilities to work in classrooms. In case supervision practice is in line with teachers' developmental level, supervisors should give specific feedback and support, which can lead to growth and advancement (Hoque et al., 2020).

Program heads may receive further training and development programs for supervision skills, promoting collaboration and autonomy among teachers. Comprehensive support and resources should be provided for implementing effective supervisory practices, continuous improvement, and innovation in education. Finally, a culture of feedback and reflection between program heads and teachers can also continue to improve the supervision program at the educational institution.

Table 1. *Level of the Program Heads' Supervisory Practices (n=146)*

<i>Supervisory Practices</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>StDev</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Directive Practices	3.24	0.4336	Good
Collaborative Practices	3.23	0.4605	Good
Non-Directive Practices	3.18	0.3516	Good
Overall Weighted Mean	3.22	0.0321	Good

Legend: 3.25-4.00 – Very Good (VG); 2.50-3.24 – Good (G); 1.75-2.49 – Poor (P); 1.00-1.74 – Very Poor (VP)

Level of the Teachers' Teaching Efficacy

Table 2 shows the teachers' very high teaching efficacy ($MW = 3.45$; $SD = 0.0545$) as assessed by the students. This indicates that from the student's point of view, teachers had a high level of efficiency in delivering instructions, administering assessment tasks, using school resources, and classroom management. The lessons were perceptibly presented to students, assessment tasks were administered accordingly, school resources were being used to aid the learning of students, and routines and activities were being managed effectively in the class.

Teachers also showed a very high teaching efficacy in the delivery of instruction ($MW = 3.51$; $SD = 0.5073$) as rated by the students. This result suggests that the teachers carefully reviewed previous lessons to build on continuity, prompted the classed to think with probing questions, and ensured the lessons were presented in such a way that they were understood easily. They also used audio-visual resources to engage students, encourage, facilitate collaboration via activities, richly supplement content with real-world illustrations, further contribute a depth of discussion with relevant questions, and break down complex concepts for clarity. The finding could mean connecting lessons across disciplines to create a whole and giving an immediate response to and clear explanation of student questions and concerns to clear the confusion.

Regarding administering assessment tasks, the teachers also exhibited a very high efficacy ($MW = 3.46$; $SD = 0.4885$) as assessed by the student-respondents. This finding indicates that the teachers articulated expectations in assessment through instructions and evaluation transparently, with various assessment tasks to gauge various levels of learning. Fairness, accuracy, and alignment with content within the class were upheld. The teachers also ensured that the assessment aligned with learning objectives and standards, diagnosed students' strengths and weaknesses, and tailored the task complexity to suit the student's abilities. They ensured that tasks aligned with what intended learning would be taken out. The finding also implies that they allowed students to self-assess their progress, ensure relevance to real-world scenarios, and provide timely feedback to help students understand their performance.

The level of the teachers' teaching efficacy in terms of school resource utilization was also very high ($MW = 3.43$; $SD = 0.4883$) as rated by the student-respondents. This finding implies that the teachers used available teaching materials in lessons, school resources effectively, and the available technology and equipment. They modified teaching styles to maximize available resources, including textbooks and teaching aids and encouraged students to use resources such as the library and other learning resources available within the school. In addition, they adjusted the utilization of resources to fit the varied needs of the students, requested and applied for other resources and gave support if necessary for teaching and were aware of the efficient use of school resources. Lastly, they trusted their ability to use school resources appropriately to improve student learning.

The teachers also exhibited a high efficacy in classroom management ($MW = 3.48$; $SD = 0.5177$). This finding implies that teachers emphasized and upheld the classroom rules and expectations, properly managing disruptive behavior, and forming a positive and respectful classroom environment to promote good behavior. The teachers also promoted communication and enforcement of consequences for misbehavior and appropriate classroom management techniques to keep the students stay focused. Moreover, they quickly settled conflicts and interpersonal issues among the students constructively. Lastly, they regularly reminded the students of the class rules to keep discipline and respect for others' opinions during class discussions.

The findings speak of the high level of teaching efficacy as perceived by the students for the teachers. The teachers were found highly efficacious in all the constructs such as delivery of instruction, assessment task administration, resource utilization, and classroom management. They could explain lessons lucidly, administer tests fairly, utilize the available school resources effectively, and manage the class routines efficiently. More importantly, the teachers were able demonstrate competency in involving students, encouraging cooperation, and providing timely feedback, thus maintaining an environment for learning.

This study disclosed that teachers' high teaching efficacy was critical regarding student learning experiences. The findings emphasized that effective delivery in instruction, fair assessment, the utilization of school resources in a resourceful manner, and skillful classroom management made students feel a conducive learning environment. The teachers engaged the students in meaningful discussion and provided feedback with effective classroom management that could have affected student learning and even overall academic performance.

Teacher efficacy and students' academic achievement are significantly related. Several factors were shown to be influential to this relation, including the scale used in the measurements for teacher efficacy, the subfactors of teacher efficacy, and the length of the teaching experience of a teacher (Kim & Seo, 2018). The self-efficacy profiles are often related to job satisfaction, classroom climate, and teacher collaboration—a good indicator of the significant impact of teacher efficacy on many aspects of the teaching environment, which influences student learning (Perera et al., 2019). Self-efficacy beliefs for teaching math were positively related to the teacher's job satisfaction and math achievement levels in their classes. The strong impact of teacher efficacy is not only on teacher well-being but also on student learning outcomes (Perera & John, 2020).

In this regard, educational institutions may recognize and honor the teachers' efforts to increase their efficacy in teaching. Professional development courses on how to teach better, assess, use resources effectively, and manage classrooms may further empower teachers to excel in what they do. Also, a collaborative environment between peers may initiate sharing best practices and new innovative teaching methodologies to benefit the teacher and student. Finally, continuous support and resources may be provided to teachers to

enable them to continually hone their skills and adapt to the changing needs of diverse student populations.

Table 2. *Level of the Teachers' Teaching Efficacy (n= 361)*

<i>Teaching Efficacy</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>StDev</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Delivery of Instruction	3.51	0.5073	Very High
Administration of Assessment Task	3.46	0.4885	Very High
School Resource Utilization	3.43	0.4883	Very High
Classroom Management	3.48	0.5177	Very High
Overall Weighted Mean	3.45	0.0545	Very High

Legend: 3.25-4.00 – Very Good (VG); 2.50-3.24 – Good (G); 1.75-2.49 – Poor (P); 1.00-1.74 – Very Poor (VP)

Significant Relationship between the Program Heads' Supervisory Practices and Teachers' Teaching Efficacy

Table 3 shows no significant relationship between the program heads' supervisory practices and the teachers' teaching efficacy. Each construct of the program heads' supervisory practices, as rated by the teachers, was not significantly related to each construct of the teachers' teaching efficacy, as rated by the students. Supervisory practices involved how program heads supervised the teachers in carrying out their daily workloads to ensure effectiveness and productivity.

Teaching efficacy is the ability of teachers to carry out tasks related to teaching the students. It is shown in the Table that the program heads' directive supervisory practices, as perceived by the teachers, were not significantly related to the teachers' teaching efficacy in terms of the delivery of instruction ($r = 0.127$; $p = 0.127$) as perceived by the students. This finding means that other factors might be significantly affecting the teachers' teaching efficacy. Directive supervision by program heads could be insufficient to achieve considerably better instructional quality. Even though the program heads provided directive supervision to their teachers, it might not suffice to influence how teachers delivered instruction in their respective classes. A possible significance of this result lies in encouraging further exploration of other support and professional development methods for teachers. This finding encourages educational leaders to evaluate other factors that could be influencing teaching efficacy, such as teacher motivation, classroom resources, workload management, and emotional support. By shifting the focus from directive supervision to more comprehensive, teacher-centered approaches that address these underlying factors, schools could potentially improve instructional quality and, by extension, student learning outcomes. The implication is that schools and educational leaders must adopt a more nuanced and flexible supervision strategy, moving beyond directive practices to a more supportive and empowering model that acknowledges the complex needs of teachers in delivering high-quality instruction. This shift could lead to a more sustainable improvement in both teacher performance and student achievement.

As perceived by the teachers, the program heads' directive supervisory practices did not significantly relate to the teachers' teaching efficacy in administering assessment tasks ($r = 0.069$; $p = 0.411$) as perceived by the student-respondents. This finding implies that how the program heads provided directive supervision to the teachers might not always influence how they administered student assessment tasks. Furthermore, some inputs given by the program heads to the teachers were not necessarily applied by the teachers, especially in administering assessment tasks. In practice, this implies that top-down approaches to supervision may not adequately address teachers' needs in areas like assessment, which often require more nuanced, context-specific strategies. Educational leaders might need to adopt more collaborative or differentiated supervisory practices, allowing teachers greater autonomy and support tailored to their specific challenges in assessment design and execution. Additionally, professional development focused on assessment literacy and innovative assessment techniques could provide more impactful support than directive supervision alone.

The directive supervisory practices of program heads did not have a significant relationship with the teachers' teaching efficacy regarding school resource utilization ($r = 0.694$; $p = 0.260$). This finding implies that the effort of program heads in giving directions to the teachers could not be necessarily indicative of how the latter utilized the school resources. The teachers might use other ways of utilizing available resources. This highlights the need for more flexible, resource-focused professional development that empowers teachers to explore creative and effective ways to utilize materials and tools in their teaching. Rather than a one-size-fits-all directive approach, program heads could facilitate workshops or peer-sharing sessions that encourage innovation in resource use, ensuring that teachers can adapt resources to their specific classroom needs. This shift could improve resource utilization and instructional effectiveness without over-reliance on top-down directives.

In addition, the program heads' directive supervision did not relate to the teachers' classroom management ($r = 0.095$; $p = 0.255$). This finding implies that even though program heads could have provided directions on how teachers might improve their instructional practices, in some cases, teachers opted to follow their ways of managing students and classroom activities. Furthermore, rigid supervisory approaches may not effectively address the diverse classroom dynamics teachers face. Instead, program heads might consider offering more tailored, supportive guidance, such as individualized coaching or collaborative problem-solving sessions, allowing teachers to refine their management strategies based on specific classroom needs. By encouraging autonomy and flexibility, schools can better support teachers in developing classroom management techniques that align with their unique teaching styles and student populations.

The findings indicate no statistically significant correlation between program heads' directive supervisory practices and the different constructs of teaching efficacy, as perceived by students. Even though program heads are traditionally responsible for directing the

work of teachers, this study indicates that these practices, may not be directly influential to the teachers' instruction delivery, assessment administration, utilization of school resources, or classroom management techniques as apprehended by students. This means that directive supervisory practices are not enough to change teachers' teaching efficacy, which indicates that other factors are more influential in determining classroom outcomes.

These findings hold significant implications for educational leadership and management. They suggest that a one-size-fits-all approach to directive supervision may not suit the complexities of teaching and learning in different classroom contexts. Instead, educational leaders must conduct more contextualized and context-sensitive supervision, considering individual teachers' needs, teaching contexts, and student populations.

It is also shown in the Table that the program heads' collaborative practices, as perceived by the teachers, did not have a significant relationship with the teacher's teaching efficacy in terms of delivery of instruction ($r = 0.145$; $p = 0.081$). This result implies that the type of collaboration that program heads shared with teachers, as perceived by the teachers, had no significant effect on how much teachers teach efficiently. For example, even if a program head could have held collaborative meetings with teachers to strategize their lesson plans and teaching strategies, it might not translate into teachers' teaching efficacy as perceived by their students. This might be because teachers follow other ways to teach the students in the classroom discussion. The lack of a significant relationship means that factors other than those related to programs—like individual teaching styles or classroom management techniques—might be more influential. Furthermore, while collaboration is important, it should be complemented by personalized professional development and support tailored to individual teachers' instructional styles. Schools may need to focus on empowering teachers to refine their unique teaching methods and offering targeted feedback that aligns with their specific classroom environments and student needs.

The program heads' collaborative practices did not significantly relate to the teachers' administration of assessment tasks ($r = 0.124$; $p = 0.135$). This finding implies that although the program heads conducted frequent collaborative sessions wherein teachers discussed assessment procedures and shared best practices, these might not be necessarily realized in the actual administration of the assessment tasks. Hence, collaborative sessions did not significantly impact how well teachers administered assessment tasks in their classrooms as perceived by the students. In practice, this implies that collaborative efforts may need to be more targeted, with a focus on practical application and hands-on training rather than theoretical discussions. Schools could benefit from providing more concrete, context-specific support for assessment design and implementation, ensuring that collaboration leads to actionable improvements in teachers' assessment administration.

It is further disclosed that the program heads' collaborative supervisory practices did not relate to the teacher's school resource utilization ($r = 0.128$; $p = 0.123$). This finding implies that if program heads often collaborated with teachers to apportion resources and choose teaching materials, the collaborative supervisory practices, despite everything, were not linked significantly to students' perceptions of the teachers' use of resources in the classroom. Moreover, this implies that collaborative efforts regarding resource management may need to be more aligned with teachers' actual classroom needs and how they engage with those resources. Schools could consider offering more individualized support, allowing teachers to experiment and adapt resources creatively, rather than focusing solely on collaborative decision-making processes.

In addition, the program heads' collaborative supervisory practices were not significantly related to the teachers' classroom management ($r = 0.148$; $p = 0.075$). This implies that the collaborative approach of program heads in supervising the teachers on how classrooms should be managed did not sufficiently influence how teachers managed their classes on the student's perceptions. Additionally, this implies that collaborative discussions on classroom management may not address the individual preferences or real-time challenges teachers face in managing their classrooms. Schools might need to offer more personalized support or training, allowing teachers to develop management techniques that align with their unique teaching styles and classroom dynamics rather than relying on general collaborative strategies.

The findings show that teachers' perceptions of program heads' collaborative practices were not related to the teachers' teaching efficacy. The finding indicates that collaboration among program heads and teachers, as conducted, may be emphasized in improving the program. However, the level of collaboration may not necessarily influence the teachers on their day-to-day teaching practices.

This study shows that educational leaders should focus on building collaborative practices. Policies cannot be easily translated into concrete pedagogic outcomes but require other factors to be in place, such as individual teacher qualities, classroom dynamics, and modes of instruction. There is the need for a better understanding of the role of collaboration in program initiatives by highlighting the importance of matching it with specific goals and strategies, which can be adapted to cater to the needs of teachers and students.

The program heads' non-directive supervisory practices did not show a significant relationship with the teachers' teaching efficacy in the delivery of instruction ($r = 0.044$; $p = 0.599$). This finding implies that despite the program heads adopting a non-directive approach, allowing teachers a high degree of autonomy in their teaching methods, it still did not appear influential in how teachers delivered instruction as perceived by the students. This suggests that while autonomy is valuable, it may not be sufficient on its own to improve instructional quality; teachers might benefit from more structured support or targeted resources that help bridge the gap between autonomy and effective teaching. Schools could consider implementing a hybrid approach that combines autonomy with ongoing guidance and feedback, ensuring that teachers have the tools and support necessary to optimize their instructional practices.

Similarly, the program heads' non-directive practices and teachers' administration of assessment tasks had no significant relationship ($r = 0.022$; $p = 0.795$). Though program heads provided some autonomy to teachers regarding what assessment methods they wanted to use, there was no strong correlation between how the teachers administered the assessments within classrooms. Other factors, such as teacher training in assessment methodologies, might influence how teachers administered classroom assessments. This implies that program heads should consider supplementing non-directive practices with targeted training and professional development focused on assessment methodologies, ensuring that teachers have the necessary skills to implement their chosen methods effectively. Additionally, fostering a culture of sharing best practices among teachers could provide valuable insights that enhance assessment administration and improve student learning outcomes.

The program heads' non-directive supervision practices did not correlate with the teachers' school resource utilization ($r = 0.23$; $p = 0.787$). In some instances, the program heads' approach allowing teachers their freedom to utilize school resources to aid instruction was not significantly associated with how the teachers were utilizing the resources in the classroom based on the student's perception. It might be because students perceived differently how the teachers utilized school resources in the classroom compared to how the program head supervised to do so. Furthermore, this suggests that simply providing autonomy may not be sufficient; teachers may require additional guidance or training on effective resource utilization to ensure that their methods align with student needs and expectations. Schools could enhance resource utilization by fostering collaboration among teachers to share strategies and best practices, thus bridging the gap between autonomy and effective classroom implementation as perceived by students.

Lastly, the relationship between the non-collaborative supervision of program heads and the teachers' classroom management ($r = 0.007$; $p = 0.935$) was statistically not significant. This implies that the program head's non-directive supervision did not influence how teachers managed their students and activities inside the classroom. Moreover, this indicates that teachers may require more structured support and interactive feedback rather than a non-collaborative approach to improve their classroom management techniques. Schools could benefit from implementing collaborative supervision models that encourage regular dialogue and shared strategies among teachers, fostering an environment where effective classroom management can be developed and refined.

Table 3. Significant Relationship between the Program Heads' Supervisory Practices and the Teachers' Teaching Efficacy

Constructs	Delivery of Instructions	Administration of Assessment Tasks	School Resource Utilization	Classroom Management
Directive Practices	$r = 0.127$ $p = 0.127$ Accept Ho	$r = 0.069$ $p = 0.411$ Accept Ho	$r = 0.694$ $p = 0.260$ Accept Ho	$r = 0.095$ $p = 0.255$ Accept Ho
Collaborative Practices	$r = 0.145$ $p = 0.081$ Accept Ho	$r = 0.124$ $p = 0.135$ Accept Ho	$r = 0.128$ $p = 0.123$ Accept Ho	$r = 0.148$ $p = 0.075$ Accept Ho
Non-Directive Practices	$r = 0.044$ $p = 0.599$ Accept Ho	$r = 0.022$ $p = 0.795$ Accept Ho	$r = 0.023$ $p = 0.787$ Accept Ho	$r = 0.007$ $p = 0.935$ Accept Ho

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between the program heads' supervisory practices and teachers' teaching efficacy.
 Legend: 0.00-0.01** Highly Significant; 0.02-0.05* Significant; above 0.05 Not Significant

The findings imply that the non-directive supervisory practices of program heads, as assessed by the teachers, did not significantly relate to different dimensions of teaching efficacy, such as delivering instruction, administering assessment tasks, school resource utilization, and classroom management as perceived by the students. This non-directive supervision, which program heads employed, did not appear to be related to teachers' teaching efficacy. These findings did not affirm the benefits of these non-directive approaches, such as encouraging autonomy and self-reflection among teachers, because their direct consequences on teaching efficacy was not supported in the study.

These findings, however, have important implications for educational leadership and support systems for teachers. Even though non-directive supervision practices are often lauded as likely to encourage autonomy and self-reflection among teachers, the apparent disconnect from what is known to be essential elements of teaching efficacy focuses on the complexity of using supervision to support effective teaching practices. It requires a better understanding of the role of supervision in teacher development. The systems must be defined to offer a targeted, context-specific support and feedback mechanism that meets the diverse needs of teachers. The best approach for educational leaders is an integrative one that bridges the balance between autonomy and structured support mechanisms, allowing for continuous development and improvement among teachers while considering the multifaceted teaching effectiveness.

Various pieces of literature claimed that supervision significantly affected teachers' efficacy. In some instances, it did not always apply. Supervisory practices did not relate to teachers' efficacy and effectiveness (Hoque et al., 2020). In addition, no relationship has been found between instructional coaching and efficacy in inclusive pedagogy, classroom management, and collaboration (Jenkins, 2021). Lastly, a weak relationship was found between the perceived impact of instructional supervision and overall teacher efficacy. Though

not significant, it was confirmed that the more needs the teacher had, the more influence the coaching process had on the teacher's sense of efficacy. The more the teacher could be confident in coaching focus, the less impact instructional coaching was perceived (Walsh et al., 2020).

Overall, the results of this study did not find a significant relationship between program heads' supervisory practices and teachers' teaching efficacy. Whether directive, collaborative, or non-directive, supervision did not affect teachers' efficacy in delivering instruction, administering assessment tasks, using school resources, or managing the classroom. Such result points to the complex role of supervision in improving teaching effectiveness. Individual teacher's needs and the specificity of the instructional context should be considered when designing supervisory frameworks and support systems in educational settings.

Conclusions

Program heads across directive, collaborative, and non-directive practices demonstrated good supervisory behavior, hence an enabling environment that supports effective teaching and professional development. The teachers perceived program heads to be involved in instructional supervision, provided clear guidance, and shared a sense of collaboration. Effective supervision of program heads is essential in guiding teachers into performing quality teaching that will lead towards the betterment of student learning outcomes. The program heads can improve their supervisory practices through firstly, they may invest in ongoing training focused on effective supervisory strategies, classroom management techniques, and assessment practices. This training can equip program heads with the skills needed to support teachers more effectively. Secondly, they may create structured opportunities for collaboration among teachers, such as regular team meetings or peer observation sessions. This can facilitate sharing best practices and collective problem-solving in instructional strategies and classroom management. Lastly, establish a culture of continuous feedback where program heads regularly provide constructive feedback to teachers and encourage self-reflection. This could include post-observation discussions and collaborative goal setting. This will ensure that educational supervision keeps developing and becomes innovative to the benefit of both teachers and students.

The teaching efficacy for the teachers as perceived by their students was high regarding instruction delivery, administering assessments, resource utilization, and classroom management. High efficacy means that the teacher can deliver the lesson effectively, administering a fair assessment, optimally utilizing school resources, and keeping the classroom environment orderly and pleasant. These competencies greatly help in building an enabling environment that promotes learning and improves the performance of students. This study brings out the importance of teacher's efficacy in the enhancement of learning experience and outcomes of students. To sustain and further improve these levels of efficacy, educators should be provided with continuous professional development on a systematic and sustained basis, catalytic and collaborative environment, and resources and support intervention designed to uniquely fit the needs of teachers.

No significant relationship was found between the program heads' directive, collaborative, or non-directive supervisory practices and teachers' teaching efficacy in delivering instruction, administering assessments, using school resources, and managing classrooms. This implies that the supervisory practices of the program heads do not directly influence the efficacy of teachers as perceived by the students. These findings underline the complexity of supervision's role in enhancing teaching effectiveness and suggest that other factors might be more influential in teaching efficacy, such as individual teacher qualities and classroom dynamics related to contextual consideration. Educational leaders should be provided with the direction at an appropriate level against the needs of teachers and their unique classroom contexts to optimize teaching efficacy by adopting a more flexible and targeted approach-one that balances autonomy with structured support.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Elton John B. Embodo, EdD

Pangabuan Integrated School

Department of Education – Philippines

Haydee D. Villanueva, PhD
Misamis University – Philippines